

SIZE EFFECTS ON PLAIN AND FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETES AT HIGH LOADING RATES

Sidney Mindess¹ and Klaus-Alexander Rieder²

¹*Department of Civil Engineering, University of British Columbia
2324 Main Mall, Vancouver, British Columbia V6T 1Z4, Canada*

²*W.R. Grace & Co.-Conn., CC&MP Laboratory
62 Whittemore Avenue, Cambridge, Massachusetts 02140, U.S.A.*

SUMMARY: This study was carried out to evaluate the size dependence of the maximum stress and the fracture energy of fibre reinforced concrete under impact. Impact tests were carried out using a large instrumented drop-weight impact machine. The impact loads were applied as line loads along the centre lines of the top and bottom faces of concrete cubes, thereby inducing a state of splitting tension. The tests were performed at different drop heights (i.e., loading rates) to investigate the influence of the loading rate on the size effect. The concrete cubes, ranging in size from 101.6mm to 406.4mm, contained discontinuous fibers of either steel or polypropylene. It was found that the fracture energy increased considerably as both size and loading rate were increased; the effects on strength were slight.

KEYWORDS: concrete, impact, size effect, steel fibres, polypropylene fibres, splitting tension, strength, fracture energy.

INTRODUCTION

It has long been known that concrete is a stress-rate sensitive material [1-5], and that the fracture parameters obtained under quasi-static loading conditions cannot be generalized to predict the fracture behavior of concrete subjected to impact loads [3,5]. It is also well known that there is a considerable size effect on concrete strength and fracture parameters, with larger specimens generally exhibiting lower strengths than smaller ones [e.g. 6]. However, to date there have been no systematic studies of the interrelationship between size effects and stress rate effects; the present work is one step in that direction.

Moreover, plain concrete is a brittle material, with low tensile strength and strain capacities, and low toughness. The addition of discontinuous fibers enhances these properties; the fibers act to reduce the stress at the crack tips by bridging across the matrix cracks that develop when the concrete is loaded. Fibres have been found to be particularly effective in helping the concrete to withstand impact loads [7]. In this study, the rate effects and size effects were examined for both plain and fibre reinforced concretes.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Impact tests

An instrumented drop-weight impact machine was used to generate the impact loads. This machine is shown in *Fig. 1* and is described in detail elsewhere [8-10] Briefly, it is capable of dropping a mass of 543 kg from heights up to 2.4 m onto the specimen, giving a kinetic energy of up to 11,590 Joules. The impact loads were applied as line loads along the center lines of the top and bottom faces of the cubes. This induces tensile stresses perpendicular to the direction of loading (“splitting tension”). Attached to the bottom of the falling mass is the striking tup, which is instrumented with four electric resistance strain gauges, connected together to form a Wheatstone bridge circuit. The specimen rests on a linear support, which is also instrumented. The signals from the tup and the support were recorded at 4 μ s intervals, using a high-speed PC-based data acquisition system.

After signal processing, the load as a function of time was obtained. The kinetic energy transferred from the falling hammer to the specimen was simply considered as the fracture energy in the impact tests, neglecting the kinetic energies of the specimen halves after the samples were split. The work W_{ha} done by the applied load during the entire impact event can be calculated using the impulse-momentum relationship of the hammer:

$$W_{ha} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot M_h \cdot \left[\left(\frac{1}{M_h} \cdot \int p(t) \cdot dt + \sqrt{2 \cdot g_c \cdot h} \right)^2 - 2 \cdot g_c \cdot h \right] \quad (1)$$

where M_h is the mass of the hammer, h is the drop height, g_c is the corrected gravitational acceleration, and $p(t)$ is the time dependent load of the hammer during the impact event. A correction factor has to be applied to obtain the corrected gravitational acceleration, to account for frictional effects between the hammer and the guiding columns and the air resistance ($g_c=0.91g$, where g is the acceleration due to gravity).

Static tests

The static tests were carried out using the same shapes for the support and the tup loading device as were used for the impact tests. The so-called Brazil test was first used by Carneiro [11] This test method seems to provide reliable data for the tensile strength of concrete as shown in [12,13] The splitting procedure was performed using a rigid testing machine with a maximum load capacity of 150 kN operating in a displacement controlled mode with a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The value of the static as well as the dynamic splitting tensile strength f_t was calculated as

$$f_t = \frac{2 \cdot P_t}{\pi \cdot a^2} \quad (2)$$

where P_t is the maximum load and “ a ” is the length of the side of the cube. Eqn 2 was also used to calculate the dynamic splitting tensile strength, although it was originally derived for static loading conditions only. No corrections to eqn 2 were made to take dynamic effects into account.

Fig. 1 543 kg drop weight impact machine.

Mixes, Materials and test specimens

The same proportions were used for the plain (control) and FRC mixes for the entire investigation. The mix designs for the NSC and HSC concretes are shown in *Table 1*. The water-to-cement ratio was maintained at 0.36 for all of the HSC specimens. The compressive strength was determined on three cylinders of each mix (101.6 mm diameter and 203.2 mm height). The average compressive strength of the NSC was 30 MPa and of the HSC was 85 MPa.

Table 1: Material per m³ of concrete mix.

	NSC	HSC
Cement, ASTM Type I	390 kg	457 kg
Sand	800 kg	645 kg
Gravel (size = 7 to 12 mm)	895 kg	1076 kg
Water	195 kg	161 l
Silica fume	-	81 kg
Superplasticizer ASTM C 494 Type A	-	3.7 – 4.5 l

Nine mixes were made for this investigation. Two were control mixes without fibers: a HSC mix and a NSC mix. The other seven mixes contained 0.5% volume percent of different fibers.

For the study of the influence of the impact velocity on the fracture energy of plain HSC, cubes with a side length of 101.6 mm were chosen, which were cast in laminated wooden moulds. Seven different impact velocities using the drop weight impact machine and tests

under quasi-static loading conditions were carried out on HSC. For each series 5 specimens were tested.

The following five types of fibers were used in this investigation, which are characterized in *Table 2*: Fiber F1 and fiber F2 are polypropylene fibers, whereas fibers F3, F4, and F5 are steel fibers.

Table 2: Fibers investigated in this study.

Fibre Code	Material	Geometry	Cross-section Shape	Length (mm)	Size (mm)
F1	Polypropylene	Straight	Circular	25	0.15 diam.
F2	Polypropylene	Straight	Circular	25	0.38 diam.
F3	Steel	Crimped	Crescent	25	3.0 x 0.8
F4	Steel	Hooked-end	Circular	30	0.5 diam.
F5	Steel	Twin-cone	Circular	35	1.0 diam.

In addition, six cubes with a side length of 203.2 mm and nine cubes with a side length of 101.6 mm were cast in laminated wooden moulds for each test series. Two different impact velocities, 2 m/s and 3 m/s, were chosen to find out whether the size effect of FRC materials is more pronounced than that of plain concrete.

Companion cylinders (203.2 mm long and 101.6 mm in diameter) were cast in plastic moulds to measure the compressive strength after 28 days of curing. All specimens were cured in lime-saturated water for 28 days before testing.

RESULTS

The average values and the standard deviations of the splitting tensile strength f_t are presented in *Table 3*. Three different loading conditions were applied to HSC and FRHSC (fiber reinforced high strength concrete): The loading rate was varied from 0.5 mm/min using a displacement controlled INSTRON machine, to 2 m/s and 3 m/s using the drop weight impact machine.

Table 3 Splitting tensile strength at various loading conditions.

Side length of the cube: 102.6 mm	Static loading 0.5 mm/min		Impact velocity: 2 m/s		Impact velocity: 3 m/s	
	Mean	$\pm \Delta$	Mean	$\pm \Delta$	Mean	$\pm \Delta$
HSC, fiber 1	3.2	0.7	7.2	0.1	7.2	3.2
HSC, fiber 2	4.2	0.8	4.2	1.8	7.1	3.1
HSC, fiber 3	4.2	0.4	6.1	1.0	5.7	0.2
HSC, fiber 4	4.1	0.4	5.5	1.9	5.7	1.3
HSC, fiber 5	3.8	0.4	8.5	2.3	10.7	1.7
HSC, no fibers	3.9	0.4	6.1	2.0	6.3	1.6

In Fig. 3 (a) the impact energy is plotted as a function of the impact velocity. This test series was carried out on plain HSC cubes with a side length of 101.6 mm. Fig. 3 (b) shows the maximum load of the hammer at different impact velocities. As it can be seen from these two diagrams, there is hardly any correlation between the impact velocity and the maximum load of the impact, if the specimen size is relatively small. The dynamic splitting energy or impact energy increases as the impact velocity increases. It should be noted again that the kinetic energies of the specimen halves after the samples were split were neglected.

Fig. 2 (a) The dynamic splitting energy and (b) the maximum load of the striking hammer of HSC at different impact velocities.

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 show typical load versus time curves of the tup and the support load cell of concrete reinforced with 0.5 vol.% of crimped steel fibers at two different impact velocities. The curves in Fig. 4 represent the results obtained with a 101.6 mm cube, whereas in Fig. 5 the results obtained with a 203.2 mm cube are summarized. It is obvious that the load versus time curves of the small samples are very similar at different impact velocities, whereas quite a difference can be observed when larger specimens are tested at different impact velocities.

A closer look at Fig. 6 and especially at Fig. 7 reveals that the standard deviation of these tests is relatively high. In Fig. 6 the specific impact energy of all the materials is presented. The specific impact energy is equal to the impact energy divided by the fracture surface area (plane fracture surface area assumed). From the results it can be seen that the specific impact energy increases with increasing specimen size. This effect is more pronounced in the case of HSC or HSFRC; it is less obvious in the case of NSC or NSFRC.

The results of the dynamic splitting tensile strengths of all the tested materials are summarized in Fig. 7. There is hardly any difference in the splitting tensile strengths at different impact velocities, which is probably due to the fact that the difference between the two impact velocities was too small. The influence of the specimen size on the splitting tensile strength could be observed; the strength generally decreased with increasing specimen size.

Fig. 8 shows the ratio of the maximum load of the support to the maximum load of the tup load cell. It is very interesting to notice that the difference between the maximum load at the support and the maximum load of the top tends to increase with increasing specimen size and increasing impact velocity. In the case of plain NSC or HSC the maximum load of the support was 40% higher than the maximum load of the tup load cell. This phenomenon is at least partly due to the additional inertia forces from the accelerated specimens, which are transferred to the support load cell.

Fig. 3 Load versus time curves of the tup and the support at different impact velocities. FRC cubes have a side length of 101.6 mm.

Fig. 4 Load versus time curves of the tup and the support at different impact velocities. FRC cubes have a side length of 203.2 mm.

Fig. 5 The specific impact energy of FRC with a fiber content of 0.5 vol.%.

Fig. 6 The dynamic splitting tensile strength of FRC with a fiber content of 0.5 vol.%.

Fig. 7: The ratio between the maximum load of the tup and the maximum load of the support of FRC with a fiber content of 0.5 vol.%.

DISCUSSION

From the experimental data, it may be seen that the presence of fibers at the relatively low addition rate of 0.5% by volume had little or no effect on the splitting tensile strength, under either static or impact loading. This is consistent with the general observation that much higher fiber volumes (>1.5%) are required before the splitting tensile strength exhibits any significant increase. However, the fibers, and in particular the steel fibers, did lead to significant increases in the energy absorbed on impact. This is a more useful contribution of the fibers than would be an increase in strength, since the latter can be achieved more easily and economically in other ways.

The load versus time curves (Figs. 3 and 4), from which the fracture energies were derived, do show a significant size effect. For the small specimens, these curves are independent of impact velocity, while for the larger specimens this is no longer true. As well, the specific impact energies increase with increasing specimen size. Thus, splitting tension tests are both size and rate dependent, though the reasons for this are not entirely clear. The experimental data summarized by Bazant and Planas [6] display considerable disparities, probably related to the experimental details of the various tests described. It is thus not surprising that more clearly defined trends could not be obtained from the present work. It may be that a more detailed analysis of the experimental results, in which both the kinetic energies of the specimen halves after splitting, and the associated inertial forces are considered, might help to clarify these data.

It should be noted that all of the impact data, as may be seen in *Figs. 5-7*, exhibited a fair amount of experimental scatter. This appears to be a problem inherent to impact testing, which no one has been able to overcome satisfactorily.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results presented above, it may be concluded that:

1. The dynamic splitting energy (impact energy) increases as the impact velocity increases.
2. The splitting tensile strength increases markedly from static loading to impact loading; however, the further increase in strength from an impact velocity of 2 m/s to one of 3 m/s was only slight.
3. The splitting tensile strength generally decreases with increasing specimen size.
4. However, the specific impact energy increases with increasing specimen size, particularly for the high strength concretes.
5. The load versus time responses of the specimens at different impact velocities are influenced by specimen size. Smaller specimens did not display much difference at different impact velocities, but the response curves for the larger specimens were quite different at different impact velocities.

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